

Katayev Salaxiddin Valiquil o'g'li

Teacher of Termez Institute of Agrotechnology and Innovative Development

Abstract. People take IELTS for various reasons — and they usually know what score they need. Some want to get an IELTS Certificate (this is probably the most common reason for taking the exam), while others plan to immigrate to an English speaking country or to work in an area where one needs a good command of English.

Key words: abroad, IELTS, university, student, education.

IELTS for education

If you are interested in studying abroad, remember that many universities around the world and almost all UK universities and colleges recognize the results of IELTS tests.

The UK, US, Canada, New Zealand, and Australia are among the most popular destinations to go studying to after you obtain an IELTS certificate. If you want to become a student in the United Kingdom, you can take a look at opportunities for foreigners on the [British Council](#)'s website, and if you are interested in a master's or doctoral program, then check at [UCAS](#).

More than 3,300 higher education institutions and programs in the United States (Visiting Programs, [Fulbright Scholarships](#), Bachelor's, Master's, Ph.D., MBA, etc.) take IELTS scores as confirmation of English proficiency.

IELTS is preferred and recognized by more than 290 educational institutions in [Canada](#). Canada also offers numerous grants for international students and scholars, as well as for Canadians who study and conduct a research abroad. The Government of Canada, foreign governments, non-governmental and international organizations provide these grants and scholarships.

Australia has the third largest number of international students in the world after the United Kingdom and the United States, despite the country's population of only 23 million. This is not surprising considering that Australia has 7 of the top 100 universities in the world! In fact, with more than 22,000 courses in 1,100 educational establishments, Australia ranks above countries such as Germany, the Netherlands, and Japan, the eighth in the Universities 2012 U21 national higher education ranking. On the [Australian Government's official website](#) for international students, you can find courses, institutions, and scholarships, read about Australia's study and life, other students' stories, and learn about Australian education.

If you are considering a bachelor's or master's degree program, it is best for you to take the IELTS academic test. General IELTS test is sufficient for non-degree programs. When choosing a college or university, check out which version of IELTS is right for you.

In order to become a foreign student, you will need to demonstrate that you are qualified and can successfully complete the English program. Therefore, you need to get a higher IELTS score for your master's or doctoral degree.

To obtain a student visa, you need to get at least 6 out of 9 points in each section. Requirements for the number of IELTS points may vary depending on the institution. For admission to postgraduate or doctoral studies, a minimum score of at least 6.5 is required. This means a minimum of 6 points in all four IELTS sections.

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For professional courses such as nursing, medicine, etc., IELTS scores are required to be a minimum of 7 points. A score of 7 means at least 6.5 points in each section: Reading, Writing, Listening, Speaking.

Many European universities also accept applicants with IELTS results other than mentioned above. For example, [this website](#) has a list of universities in Europe that accept foreign students with IELTS score of 5.0 to 7.0.

Whichever university you choose, bear in mind that in addition to IELTS, each university also has entrance exams that need to be prepared. We recommend visiting the program or the university website for more information on IELTS scores.

IELTS for employment

Proof of your English language skills is an important stage in obtaining a visa so you can work abroad. Language proficiency is a key to career success and is considered a valuable asset in addition to all other requirements in any job. If you are applying for a work visa, you must have an appropriate level of language skills, which means that you need to be able to speak not only basic spoken English.

For the UK, applicants must score at least 6.5 points for each of the four sections of the test (reading, speaking, listening and writing).

To work in Australia, test score 5 is considered to be “professional English”. A score of 6 means that the applicant is a “competent English speaker”.

In New Zealand, applicants must score a total score of 4 or higher in IELTS general or academic. They may also be asked to provide additional evidence of English proficiency, such as information about the countries in which they lived; their country of current residence, or knowledge of English in their family.

In Canada, applicants should contact the organization to which they wish to apply directly to clarify the requirements for IELTS scores. Employers and educational institutions usually set their own language requirements.

For all these countries, keep in mind that the minimum score requirements vary depending on the profession you choose. For some professions, candidates must score a minimum of 6 points in each of the sections of the test, whereas for teachers, for example, a minimum score of 7 is required.

Remember that IELTS is the first step to achieving your dream. If you decide to leave your home to study abroad, build a career or move to another country, IELTS certification will help you to open new horizons and other opportunities.

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